

Blockchain Adoption and International Trade Performance: Evidence from Panel ARDL Analysis of BRICS Economies

Muhammad MARENAH ^a

a: Researcher, İstanbul Ticaret University, Department of Digital Economics and Marketing, İstanbul, Türkiye, 0009-0002-0357-2760, u23tdei802@istanbulticaret.edu.tr

Submitted: 07.04.2026, Accepted: 17.04.2026, Published: 25.04.2026

Cite APA: Marenah, M., (2026). Blockchain Adoption and International Trade Performance: Evidence from Panel ARDL Analysis of BRICS Economies, Journal of İstanbul School of Technology (JISTECH), 2(1), pp 180-202, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19655406

ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of blockchain adoption on international trade performance in BRICS economies using panel data over the period 2010–2024. Employing the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (P-ARDL) model, the analysis distinguishes between short-run and long-run dynamics while accounting for cross-country heterogeneity. The results indicate that blockchain adoption has a statistically significant and positive effect on trade performance in the long run, primarily by enhancing transaction efficiency, transparency, and trust in cross-border exchanges. In the short run, however, the effects are mixed, reflecting adjustment costs, technological barriers, and varying levels of digital infrastructure across countries. The findings remain robust after controlling key macroeconomic variables, including GDP, exchange rates, and trade openness. This study aligns with existing empirical evidence on the trade-enhancing role of blockchain in BRICS economies, a topic that has received limited attention. The results suggest that policies promoting digital infrastructure, regulatory clarity, and technological adoption can strengthen trade integration and economic cooperation among BRICS members.

Keywords: *International Trade, Blockchain Technology, Cointegrating regression, Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag, BRICS*

1. INTRODUCTION

BRICS is increasingly challenging the dominance of Western nations and institutions in international trade, accounting for 24% of global trade (Kumar et al., 2024). The bloc aims to increase its share in the global market by de-dollarizing its trade transactions (Aggarwal, 2020). Shifting trade settlements away from the U.S. dollar protects BRICS economies from sanctions and trade embargoes imposed by the United States (Liu & Papa, 2022). Cross-border trade transactions denominated in U.S. dollars expose countries to exchange rate volatility, which increases transaction and production costs. Consequently, BRICS members are engaging in local currency trade settlements to reduce their dependence on the U.S. dollar, which may reshape global trade dynamics over time (Nach & Nwadi, 2024; Siddiqui, 2016). For example, China and Russia facilitate bilateral trade using the Chinese yuan and Russian ruble. However, the transition is hindered by the absence of a unified currency. The introduction of a single BRICS currency could enhance coordination among its members and strengthen their purchasing power, given their collective currency reserves.

One option the bloc is considering for a BRICS currency is a blockchain-based currency. currency eliminates the need for intermediaries in transactions, helps cut down costs, and improves the efficiency of international trade (Wang et al., 2019). Payments via blockchain systems ensure more reliable and faster cash flow for businesses. Studies indicate that remittances conducted via blockchain-based platforms are more flexible, cost-effective, and dependable than SWIFT and other traditional transfer methods (Chen & Bellavitis, 2020). Transfers through conventional financial systems are expensive, involve numerous bureaucratic procedures, may take days to be completed, and are restricted in some countries (Dyhrberg & Haubo, 2015). If cryptocurrency payments are integrated into more e-commerce platforms, this could expand e-commerce due to lower transaction costs and greater transparency, giving merchants the opportunity to sell in

countries with different payment infrastructures (Ying et al., 2018). Blockchain-based systems are universally accessible and mitigate traders' exposure to exchange rate fluctuations (Ganne, 2018). The cryptographic nature of these systems can help businesses avoid fraudulent transactions and corrupt practices, ensuring secure and transparent dealings (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016). Every transaction is documented in an immutable ledger, allowing thorough verification and reducing the need for costly audits. Businesses can also leverage smart contracts to provide security, automation, and transparency in procurement processes such as online bidding (Zheng et al., 2017). Blockchain can also be used for tracking deliverables. Utilizing smart contracts in trade may enhance BRICS foreign trade volume and reduce trade risks (Aggarwal, 2020). Approximately 80% of global trade is financed using traditional methods such as Letters of Credit (LCs). The payment process for LCs takes between 7 and 10 days to complete, whereas smart contracts can autonomously process payments upon the fulfillment of stipulated terms (WTO, 2016).

Existing literature highlights that costs in cross-border trade and trade finance can be reduced by integrating blockchain technology into financial institutions' systems (Belu, 2019). Empirical evidence also shows that trust between trading partners stimulates an increase in trade flows (den Butter & Mosch, 2003). This study contributes to the existing literature by examining the impact of blockchain adoption on international trade in emerging economies such as the BRICS nations. The empirical evidence provides insights for businesses and governments considering blockchain-based payment platforms and currencies for cross-border trade. Although the integration of blockchain in international trade is increasingly discussed by governments and corporations, empirical evidence remains limited. Current studies primarily concentrate on supply chain aspects of blockchain (Öz & Göre, 2019).

The paper fills this gap by analyzing the impact of blockchain adoption, proxied by cryptocurrency indicators, on international trade. It contributes to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence from BRICS economies. This study aims to investigate

whether the use of blockchain-based systems optimizes international trade flows among BRICS countries. It also examines whether blockchain can offset the adverse effects of factors such as exchange rate volatility and trade costs on global trade growth.

The rest of this study is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the related literature. Section 3 explains the data and methodology used. Section 4 presents and interprets the results, and the final section concludes

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Blockchain technology is rooted in the work of Haber and Stornetta (1991), who developed a system that digitally time-stamps electronic documents to prevent tampering and misdating. It further evolved into a distributed and decentralized ledger that enables direct transactions between users (Nakamoto, 2008). Each transaction on a blockchain is cryptographically recorded as a bidirectionally connected chain of blocks. These features give the technology an advantage over banks, remittance agencies, and other traditional payment systems (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016).

Various researchers have conducted studies on blockchain and international trade. Crosby et al. (2016) revealed that blockchain is being used in multiple sectors, such as supply chains, finance, and healthcare, to improve transparency, increase trust, and mitigate risks related to fraud and counterfeiting in international trade. This argument was supported by Kshetri (2018), who examined cases in which international trade was optimized through blockchain, highlighting its benefits for trade. Belu (2019) explains that integrating blockchain into financial and payment systems may transform international trade, as the technology's low transaction costs streamline payment processes and facilitate trade financing. According to Gartner (2018), the contribution of blockchain to international trade value is estimated to increase from \$38 billion in 2018 to \$360 billion in 2026 and is predicted to exceed \$3 trillion by 2030. Chang, Chen, et al. (2019) explored ways to leverage blockchain to expedite the flow of logistics, documents, and cash in global trade cycles. Galvez et al. (2018) advocated for the integration of blockchain into supply chains

to maximize traceability in complex logistical networks that have emerged due to trade globalization. Similarly proposed by Cole et al. (2019) and Li et al. (2023), blockchain can boost international trade and transform procurement and logistics operations by providing data integrity, accountability, and end-to-end traceability. Chang et al. (2020) examined how blockchain could modernize government agencies by reducing excessive paperwork and bureaucratic procedures and increasing trade flows. Chang et al. (2019) investigated the potential reshaping and modernization of trade finance with blockchain Letters of Credit. Chandan et al. (2023) discussed the application of blockchain contracts to optimize cross-border trade. The immutable feature of smart contracts makes them safe and secure for information sharing between trade stakeholders, as explained by Saberi et al. (2019). Some studies (Hastig & Sodhi, 2020; Koh et al., 2020; Okazaki, 2018) examined the use of blockchain to facilitate trade finance and combat illicit trade.

A significant number of studies have examined the theoretical aspects of blockchain's impact on international trade; however, few empirical studies exist on this subject. Siddik et al. (2021) concluded that blockchain technology positively impacts international trade, based on analysis using a generalized linear model and a VAR Granger causality test, which demonstrated a strong unidirectional causality from blockchain to international trade. An experiment by Tian et al. (2024), conducted in collaboration with Shanghai WinJoin Information Technology Co., Ltd., provides empirical evidence that blockchain technology increases international trade in emerging markets. Lian (2022) found that international trading companies are exposed to moderate trade credit risks in blockchain-based transactions. Weerakoon and Chandanie (2021) reported that blockchain addresses inefficiencies in Sri Lanka's international trade by closing transparency gaps, facilitating information sharing between stakeholders, reducing bureaucracy, accelerating payment processes, and lowering financial costs. A numerical analysis and simulation performed by Yoon et al. (2020) indicates that blockchain accelerates international trade flows by reducing shipment lead time and ocean transport costs. Balci and Surucu-Balci (2021) underlined that insufficient understanding of blockchain remains a key obstacle to harnessing its full potential in international trade.

The e-CNY was not only created as a domestic medium of exchange; its main goal is to facilitate cross-border trade settlements (F. Allen et al, 2022). It provides China with the leverage to bypass international payment networks controlled by the United States, thereby undermining U.S. embargo coercion and creating a countermeasure against China's embargo regime (Laband, 2020). India introduced the digital rupee, which complements its Unified Payments Interface (UPI) system. This initiative may reduce the time and cost associated with cross-border payments. Private banks in India, such as YES, Axis, ICICI, and Kotak Mahindra, have conducted international trade transactions using BCT (Patki et al, 2020). In Brazil, CBDC was introduced to foster innovation in the entrepreneurial sector by supporting cryptocurrency and smart contracts (BIS, 2022). South Africa experimented to gain insight into integrating BCT into interbank payments; the country's reserve bank launched a tokenized South African Rand operating on the Khokha payment system for a 14-day trial (Liu & Papa, 2022). The pilot digital ruble, launched by the Russian central bank in 2024, is aimed at neutralizing the effects of sanctions, building a resilient financial system, and increasing trade flow with allies (Cherenkova, 2023). An estimated 100,000 transactions have been completed across the 2,500 issued wallets (Bank of Russia, 2025). Tokoin, an Indonesian company, was founded to support Indonesian Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in managing and improving business efficiency. It launched various applications to achieve this goal; the My T-wallet aggregates the purchases to minimize cross-border transaction costs. Tokobit, a blockchain platform, enables businesses to track and manage transactions, and the tokobook is a blockchain bookkeeping and financial report management application (Saputra & Darma, 2022). In the battle against counterfeits, the Egyptian customs authority mandates merchants to upload commercial invoices and other documents for imported goods to the CargoX blockchain for pre-verification before shipping-in is authorized (Chistruga, 2023). Despite each member conducting their own experiment on blockchain technology, the organization has a collective blockchain-based payment platform, BRICS Pay, that facilitates cross-border transactions using the local currencies of BRICS nations (Freidin, 2024). Technology, such as digital wallets and QR payments incorporated in BRICS Pay, makes it a cost-effective and user-friendly payment

system (D. Krause, 2024) and a stepping stone in establishing a zero-dollar BRICS market.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model and data

To assess whether bitcoin adoption influences international trade among BRICS economies, this study specifies an econometric framework in which trade openness is modeled as a function of bitcoin prices alongside additional explanatory variables outlined in Eq. (1). A balanced panel dataset is compiled for these variables, covering seven BRICS nations from 2010 to 2024, with the study period dictated by data availability constraints. The countries included are Brazil, Egypt, Russia, Indonesia, India, South Africa, and China, while Iran, Ethiopia, and the United Arab Emirates are omitted due to limited historical data.

$$LTR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LNBC_{it} + \beta_2 LNGDP_{it} + \beta_3 LNEXR_{it} + \beta_4 LNFDI_{it} + \beta_5 LNTFR_{it} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Table1. Definition and Sources

Variable	Definition	Unit of measurement	Source
TR	Trade (% of GDP)	%	World Bank Development Indicators
BC	Blockchain Currency (Bitcoin)	\$	finance.yahoo.com
GDP	Gross Domestic Product (Current \$)	\$	World Bank Development Indicators
EXR	Official Exchange Rate	LCU per US\$	World Bank Development Indicators
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment	\$	World Bank Development Indicators
TFR	Tariff rate, applied, simple mean, all products	%	World Bank Development Indicators

In this study, international trade serves as the dependent variable. It is measured as the aggregate of exports and imports as a percentage of GDP. It broadly refers to the commercial transfer of goods, services, and capital across global borders, thereby increasing market share and boosting the world economy. International trade data was sourced from the World Bank data website. The primary variable of interest, blockchain, is measured by Bitcoin historical prices from 2010 to 2024. Bitcoin is a cryptocurrency

considered a medium of exchange and a commodity (Dyhrberg, 2016). Bitcoin is immutable, valuable as an investment and medium of transaction, and cost-saving for financial services. Blockchain can expand international trade by lowering transaction costs and improving security, thereby facilitating transparency and trust. Allen et al. (2019) and Juma et al. (2019) recommend the global adoption of blockchain technology to optimize international trade. The study seeks to use empirical analysis to determine whether blockchain influences international trade.

In accordance with the literature, additional control variables are included to isolate the relationship between international trade and blockchain technology. The first is nominal GDP, a monetary measure of the total market value of goods and services produced in a country during a specific period. An increase in GDP implies higher output levels and leads to increased international trade. GDP positively impacts international trade, and a positive sign is expected for this variable. Next is the exchange rate, which is the conversion rate of a country's currency to another country's currency. For this study, it reflects the ratio of the local currency unit of each country in comparison to the U.S. dollar. An increase in a country's exchange rate implies a depreciation of its currency, making imports more expensive and exports cheaper in foreign markets, which may lead to improved net trade. Exchange rate volatility impacts international trade, and a negative sign is expected for this variable. Tariffs are taxes that a country imposes on imported goods and services. An increase in tariff rates raises the prices of domestically consumed foreign goods and services and contributes to trade contraction. Tariffs negatively affect international trade.

3.2 Empirical analysis

3.2.1 Panel unit root tests

The Levin–Lin–Chu (LLC) unit root test is performed to determine the stationarity of a panel data (Levin et al., 2002). LLC test assumes a common unit root process across cross-sectional units while allowing for individual-specific intercepts. Under the null

hypothesis, each panel series is assumed to contain a unit root, whereas the alternative hypothesis assumes that all series are stationary.

The LLC test is based on the following augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) regression:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta y_{i,t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{\rho_i} \gamma_{ij} \Delta y_{it-j} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where y_{it} represents the variable for country i at time t , α_i denotes individual-specific effects, and ρ_i is the lag length selected to eliminate serial correlation. $H_0: \beta=0$ indicates the presence of a unit root, while the $H_1: \beta < 0$ implies stationarity. After estimating the regression, the LLC test constructs a pooled t-statistic based on the estimated coefficient of the lagged level variable to test the null hypothesis. After appropriate adjustments for serial correlation and heteroskedasticity, the resulting statistic follows a standard normal distribution.

The LLC test is suitable for macro panel data with moderate time dimensions, as it provides higher statistical power than individual unit root tests. However, it assumes cross-sectional independence and a homogeneous autoregressive coefficient across units, which should be considered when interpreting the results.

Heterogeneous characteristics found across cross-sectional units are accounted for by applying the Im, Pesaran, and Shin (2003) (IPS) test. Unlike the LLC test, which assumes a common autoregressive parameter, the IPS test allows the autoregressive coefficient to vary across countries. The null hypothesis assumes that all series contain a unit root, while the alternative hypothesis allows some series to be stationary. The test is based on conducting separate unit root tests for each cross-sectional unit rather than pooling the data. The individual t-statistics obtained from these regressions are then averaged across cross-sections. Let $t_{(i,T)}$ ($i=1,2,\dots,N$) denote the individual t-statistics for testing unit roots, with $E(t_{(i,T)}) = \mu$ and $V(t_{(i,T)}) = \sigma^2$. IPS test is defined as:

$$\sqrt{N} \frac{(t_{N,T} - \mu)}{\sigma} \Rightarrow N(0,1), \text{ where } t_{N,T} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N t_{i,T} \quad (3)$$

This statistic combines evidence from N individual unit root tests and follows a standard normal distribution under the null hypothesis after appropriate standardization. For balanced panel data, the test assumes that T remains constant across cross-sectional units and that $E(t_{i,T})$ and $V(t_{i,T})$ are identical for all i .

3.2.2 Panel Cointegration Test

Following the unit root tests, the Pedroni (1999, 2004) panel cointegration test is employed to examine the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables. The Pedroni test tolerates heterogeneity in the intercepts and slope coefficients across cross-sectional units. The Pedroni test is based on the following cointegration regression:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \delta_i t + \beta_i x_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

where the dependent variable is y_{it} , $x_{(i,t)}$ denotes the vector of regressors, α_i captures individual-specific effects, and $\delta_i t$ represents deterministic trends. The disturbance term ε_{it} reflects short-term deviations from the long-run equilibrium among the cointegrated variables.

The test procedure specifies null and alternative hypotheses. H_0 assumes variables are not cointegrated; H_1 assumes the presence of cointegration. Within this framework, the autoregressive coefficient conditions are defined as $H_0: \rho = 1$ and $H_1: \rho < 1$ for all i . The statistics necessitate estimation of N autoregressive coefficients through separate equations for each cross-sectional unit, thereby allowing heterogeneity under the alternative hypothesis. In accordance with Pedroni's (1999) statistics, the estimation of

nuisance parameters from the long-run conditional variances of each unit. For panel data, Pedroni (1999) proposes seven different statistics to test for cointegration. The first four statistics, panel v , rho, PP, and ADF are categorized under within-dimension statistics, also referred to as panel statistics, which pool autoregressive coefficients across cross-sections. Group rho, PP, and ADF are between-dimension statistics category, or group statistics, which allow for heterogeneity in the autoregressive coefficients. Both sets of statistics are designed to assess the H_0 : no cointegration. Under the alternative hypothesis, the within-dimension statistics diverge towards positive infinity, and the right tail of the normal distribution is used to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration (Rault & Drine, 2002). These statistics are derived from the residuals obtained from the estimated cointegration regression. Sampling distribution of the within and between-dimension statistics by Pedroni adopting the Monte Carlo simulations. Null hypothesis is rejected if the computed test statistic exceeds the corresponding critical value (Bildirici, 2014).

3.2.3 Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (P-ARDL) model

Following confirmation of cointegration, the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is applied to estimate the short-run and long-run correlations between the variables. The Panel ARDL model is applicable when some variables stationary at order $I(0)$ and others at $I(1)$, but not $I(2)$. It allows for heterogeneity across cross-sectional units (Pesaran et al., 1999). The general form of the Panel ARDL model is specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln TR_{it} = & \alpha_i + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_{1,ij} \ln TR_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \alpha_{2,ij} \ln BT_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q2} \alpha_{3,ij} \ln GDP_{i,t-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q3} \alpha_{4,ij} \ln EXR_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q4} \alpha_{5,ij} \ln FDI_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q5} \alpha_{6,ij} \ln TFR_{i,t-j} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where $i=1,\dots,N$ represents the cross-sectional units, and $t=1,\dots,T$ signifies the time periods. α_i reflects the fixed effects unique to each unit, while $(\alpha_1 - \alpha_7)$ denotes the regressors' estimated coefficients and lagged explanatory variables. Additionally, ε_{it} are the error terms, which encompass both periods and units, and are treated as white noise. The results are expressed in as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln\Delta TR_{it} = & \alpha_i + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_{1,ij} \ln\Delta TR_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \alpha_{2,ij} \Delta BT_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q2} \alpha_{3,ij} \Delta GDP_{i,t-j} + \\
& \sum_{j=0}^{q3} \alpha_{4,ij} \Delta INEXR_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q4} \alpha_{5,ij} \Delta FDI_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q5} \alpha_{6,ij} \Delta TFR_{i,t-j} + \beta_{1,i} \ln TR_{i,t-1} + \\
& \beta_{2,i} BT_{i,t-1} + \beta_{3,i} GDP_{i,t-1} + \beta_{4,i} INEXR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{5,i} FDI_{i,t-1} + \beta_{6,i} TFR_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The first difference of the variables is denoted as Δ , coefficients for the lagged levels (β) representing long-term effects, and coefficients for the differences (α) reflecting short-term dynamics of international trade, blockchain technology (bitcoin), GDP, foreign direct investment, exchange rate, and tariffs. The short-term relationship is tested in accordance with Hendry's (1995) approach, the immediate effect of blockchain technology on international trade is evaluated using this formula

$$\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{q1} \alpha_{2,ij}}{(1 - \sum_{j=0}^p \alpha_{1,ij})}$$

taking into account only the significant coefficients. Equation 6 demonstrates the structure of the panel Error correction model, once the long-term correlation of the conditional variable and regressors is confirmed:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln\Delta TR_{it} = & \alpha_i + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_{1,itj} \ln\Delta BT_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \alpha_{2,itj} \Delta GDP_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q2} \alpha_{3,itj} \Delta EXR_{i,t-j} + \\
& \sum_{j=0}^{q3} \alpha_{4,itj} \Delta FDI_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q4} \alpha_{5,itj} \Delta TFR_{i,t-j} + \theta_i ECM_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The coefficient θ_i in the ECM signifies the annual rate at which adjustments are made to return the system to its long-term equilibrium. The optimal lag length for the ECM is determined using Akaike's information criterion, with a maximum of three lags selected due to the limited availability of annual reports.

The model is estimated using the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimator developed by Pesaran et al. (1999), which allows the short-run coefficients, intercepts, and error variances to differ across cross-sectional units while constraining the long-run

coefficients to be homogeneous. This estimator provides efficient and consistent estimates when the homogeneity assumption of long-run parameters holds. The underlying rationale for the PMG approach is that, while short-run dynamics may vary across countries due to differences in economic structures, adjustment processes, and institutional characteristics, the long-run correlation between the variables is expected to be uniform across cross-sectional units. The PMG estimator pools and averages the coefficients by estimating separate short-run equations for each unit and imposing a homogeneous long-run equilibrium relationship. This feature makes it particularly suitable for macro panel data, where countries may experience heterogeneous short-term fluctuations but converge towards a common long-run path. The approach captures the pace of adjustment through the error correction term, allowing for country-specific convergence toward equilibrium.

4. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

4.1 Unit root

Following the methodology outlined in Section 3, the stationarity of the variables is tested with the LLC and IPS panel unit root tests. Testing for stationarity validates the econometric analysis, the presence of unit root causes false regression outcomes. This section presents the stationarity test of all variables in levels and first differences. The assessments are performed using the trend and individual intercept specifications. As discussed in the methodology, the null hypothesis for the LLC and IPS panel unit root tests is that the series contains a unit root. P-values for all variable coefficients are reported and assessed at 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels to determine if null hypothesis is accepted or rejected.

Table 2. Unit Root Test

Test Type	TFR	TR	GDP	EXR	FDI
LLC					
level	-1.269 (0.102)	-0.742 (0.229)	-1.606* (0.054)	-0.764 (0.222)	-2.571*** (0.005)
First difference	-8.343***	-7.221***	-6.112***	-5.056***	-6.529*

	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
IPS					
level	0.623 (0.733)	1.204 (0.886)	0.711 (0.761)	-0.764 (0.222)	-1.567*** (0.059)
First difference	-4.340*** (0.000)	-3.831*** (0.000)	-4.283*** (0.000)	-2.727*** (0.003)	-4.756*** (0.000)

*Note: 1. P-values are in parentheses. 2. *, **, *** represent statistical significance at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.*

Table 2 contains the results from panel unit root tests for each variable, tested in levels and first differences, with individual intercepts and trends included, indicate a mixture of unit root and non-unit root variables. At the level, the results indicate that most variables are not stationary, as their p-values exceed conventional significance levels. Specifically, TFR, TR, and EXR are non-stationary under both LLC and IPS tests. GDP shows weak evidence of stationarity, as it is stationary under the LLC test but not under the IPS test. FDI, however, appears to be stationary at level under both tests, although the IPS result is only weakly significant. Overall, at level, the majority of variables have unit root. At first difference, the results from both LLC and IPS tests indicate that all variables became stationary. The p-values demonstrate statistical significance, with most significant at 1% level and the rest at the 5% or 10% levels. The null hypothesis is rejected for all variables at first difference; the variables are stationary. Based on these findings, there is no integration between the variables at order two I(2). This satisfies the requirement for applying panel ARDL modelling and subsequent cointegration analysis.

4.2 Pedroni panel cointegration

The cointegration analysis using the Pedroni (1999) methodology, as presented in Table 3, evaluates the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the panel variables. Two model specifications are employed: a within-dimension (panel) approach that assumes homogeneous autoregressive parameters, and a between-dimension (group) approach that permits cross-sectional heterogeneity.

Results of the common AR coefficients, the v-statistic, and rho-statistic are statistically insignificant, suggesting no support for cointegration under these measures. However, the panel PP-statistic and panel ADF-statistic are negative and statistically significant at the 5% level in the unweighted case and at the 1% level when weighted; therefore, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected. In the between-dimension framework, the group rho-statistic remains positive and insignificant, again failing to support cointegration. Conversely, for the individual AR coefficient, PP and ADF outputs are negative and highly significant at the 1% level, so null hypothesis is rejected.

Taken together, the evidence points to a long-run relationship among the variables. Although some panel cointegration test statistics exceed the p-value significance level, the PP and ADF statistics consistently support the presence of cointegration across the panel.

Table 3. Pedroni panel cointegration

Alternative hypothesis: common AR coefs. (within-dimension)				
	Statistic	Prob.	Weighted Statistic	Prob.
Panel v-Statistic	-1.617	0.947	-1.706	0.956
Panel rho-Statistic	2.547	0.995	2.493	0.994
Panel PP-Statistic	-2.028	0.021**	-2.850	0.002***
Panel ADF-Statistic	-1.858	0.032**	-2.429	0.007***
Alternative hypothesis: individual AR coefs. (between-dimension)				
	Statistic	Prob.		
Group rho-Statistic	3.431	0.999		
Group PP-Statistic	-7.634	0.000***		
Group ADF-Statistic	-3.659	0.000***		

*Note: 10%, 5%, and 1% represent statistical significance denoted as *, **, *** respectively*

4.3 P-ARDL results

Once it is confirmed that all variables integrate at order I(0) or I(1) but not at I(2), and cointegration exists, a panel ARDL model is estimated using the PMG estimation method. The appropriate lag length is selected based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).

The empirical results summarizing the relationship between blockchain technology and international trade, along with the control variables, are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. P-ARDL results

Long-term					Short-term			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-val	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-val
LNBC	0.0229	0.008	2.898	0.006***	-0.014	0.019	-0.722	0.473
LNGDP	0.099	0.008	13.198	0.000***	0.128	0.915	0.139	0.889
LNEXR	0.279	0.027	10.361	0.0000***	1.074	0.367	2.927	0.005***
LNFDI	0.329	0.081	4.042	0.0002***	-0.059	0.025	-2.350	0.023**
LNTFR	-0.252	0.119	-2.106	0.041**	0.119	0.200	0.596	0.553

Note: *, **, *** represent statistical significance at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

The coefficient of the error correction term (COINTEQ), which reflects the speed at which the system returns to equilibrium following short-run shocks, is -0.142. This indicates that approximately 14.2% of the deviation from long-run equilibrium in the previous period is corrected in the current period. The negative and statistically significant coefficient confirms the presence of a stable long-term correlation between international trade and the independent variables. The findings reveal that, in the long run, blockchain technology (LNBC) yields a positive and statistically significant coefficient (0.0229), indicating that a 1% increase in blockchain adoption is associated with a 2.29% increase in international trade. This reflects the growing role of blockchain in reducing transactional costs and improving trade efficiency.

Gross domestic product (LNGDP) also exhibits a positive and highly significant effect (0.099), implying 1% rise in GDP accelerates international trade by 9.9%. This supports the well-established relationship between economic growth and trade expansion. The exchange rate (LNEXR) has a positive and statistically significant coefficient (0.279), indicating that a 1% increase in the exchange rate leads to a 27.9% increase in international trade. This suggests that movements in exchange rates influence the direction and volume of trade flows between BRICS economies. Foreign direct investment (LNFDI) shows a positive and statistically significant impact (0.329), a 1%

inflow of FDI leads to a 32.9% increase in international trade. FDI is crucial in foreign trade as it may enhance production and export capacity. In contrast, tariffs (LNTFR) are negatively significant; a 1% increase in tariff rates decreases international trade by 25.2%. This reflects the trade-reducing effect of protectionist policies through increased costs of imported inputs and reduced competitiveness.

The short-run results present a different dynamic. Blockchain (LNBC) is negative (-0.014) and statistically insignificant; short-run changes of blockchain adoption do not significantly impact international trade. Similarly, GDP (LNGDP) and tariffs (LNTFR) are not statistically significant in the short run, implying that these variables do not have an immediate effect on trade flows. Exchange rate (LNEXR) is statistically positive (1.074), an increase in exchange rate by 1% stimulates a 1.074% increase in international trade in the short run. Foreign direct investment (LNFDI) is statistically significant and carries a negative coefficient (-0.059), indicating that a 1% increase in FDI leads to a 5.9% decrease in international trade in the short run. This may reflect short-term adjustment costs or lagged effects before FDI translates into productive trade-enhancing outcomes.

5. CONCLUSION

The article analyzed the impact of the blockchain-based currency Bitcoin on the international trade of BRICS nations using the ADRL approach, and the outcome confirmed that blockchain induces international trade. Overall, the analysis suggests that blockchain technology positively impacts international trade in both the short and long run. The results are supported by findings from (Siddik et al., 2021). A widespread integration of blockchain into BRICS foreign trades could stimulate trade not just within the bloc but also with the rest of the world. A trader from the bloc can benefit from low transaction costs and a faster payment scheme between suppliers or customers. They can enter other emerging markets, thanks to global accessibility of blockchain. In the future, more governments, businesses, and financial institutions are likely to embrace blockchain as they better understand its potential for international trade and trade finance. The ARDL

indicates that GDP positively influences international trade. An increase in GDP enhances a country's export capacity and specialization, appreciates the domestic currency, attracts foreign direct investment, and accelerates economic growth. We discovered that tariffs, a tool of economic protectionism, have a regressive relationship with international trade. An increase in tariffs reduces productivity, raises prices, increases unemployment, which widens the inequality gap, and causes global tensions. We observed that exchange rate movements positively affect international trade when a country's currency is devalued against the dominant traded currency (the U.S. dollar), making its exports more affordable and competitive in global markets.

Policy Recommendation

To develop a blockchain-based currency, it is necessary for the bloc to establish a joined blockchain development and research centre. The centre may be utilized for research on blockchain scalability, privacy-preservation and developing a currency suitable for the BRICS economies. The proposed currency from the research should be pegging the currency to gold prices to maintain value stability and be a source of assurance for traders. A shared blockchain financial system should be created to facilitate transactions with the BRICS cryptocurrency. Introducing a blockchain system would be a substitute for international money transfer systems (for example, SWIFT). However, transactions need to be of low cost or zero fee to stimulate cross-border trade volume. It is advised that blockchain literacy and financial inclusion programs be launched to promote the adoption of the technology by farmers and small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The currency would be more accessible if is made compatible for transactions on existing blockchain platforms, which might increase global payments and remittances with the BRICS currency. Blockchains are prone to cyberattacks; cybersecurity protocols need to be integrated into the developed system to prevent fraud and hacks. In addition, Know Your Customer (KYC) and financial crime prevention protocols should be implemented to ensure compliance with international regulatory policies while preserving financial privacy.

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, P. (2020). On de-risking and de-dollarizing intra-BRICS trade via smart contracts. *BRICS Journal of Economics*, 1(4), 54–69. <https://doi.org/10.38050/2712-7508-2020-1-4-6>
- Allen, D. W. E., Berg, C., Davidson, S., Novak, M., & Potts, J. (2019). International policy coordination for blockchain supply chains. *Asia & the Pacific Policy Studies*, 6(3), 367–380. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app5.281>
- Balci, G., & Surucu-Balci, E. (2021). Blockchain adoption in the maritime supply chain: Examining barriers and salient stakeholders in containerized international trade. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 156, 102539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2021.102539>
- Belu, M. G. (2019). Application of Blockchain in International Trade: An Overview. 71.
- Bildirici, M. (2004a). Political instability and growth: an econometric analysis of Turkey, Mexico, Argentina and Brazil, 1985-2004.
- Bildirici, M. (2004b). Real cost of employment an Turkish labour market: a panel cointegration tests approach. *International Journal of Applied Econometrics and Quantitative Studies*, 1(2), 95-120.
- Chandan, A., John, M., Potdar, V., Chandan, A., John, M., & Potdar, V. (2023). Achieving UN SDGs in Food Supply Chain Using Blockchain Technology. *Sustainability*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032109>
- Chang, S. E., Chen, Y.-C., & Wu, T.-C. (2019). Exploring blockchain technology in international trade: Business process re-engineering for letter of credit. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-12-2018-0568>
- Chang, S. E., Luo, H. L., Chen, Y., Chang, S. E., Luo, H. L., & Chen, Y. (2019). Blockchain-Enabled Trade Finance Innovation: A Potential Paradigm Shift on Using Letter of Credit. *Sustainability*, 12(1).

- Cherenkova, S. A. (2023). Advantages and potential risks of introducing the digital ruble in modern Russia. *Национальная Безопасность / Nota Bene*, (1), 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.7256/2454-0668.2023.1.39797>
- Chistruga, A. (2023). Using blockchain technology to combat counterfeiting. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 177, 02004. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202317702004>
- Saputra, U. W. E., & Darma, G. S. (2022). The Intention to Use Blockchain in Indonesia Using Extended Approach Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). *CommIT (Communication and Information Technology) Journal*, 16(1), 27–35. <https://doi.org/10.21512/commit.v16i1.7609>
- Chang, Y., Iakovou, E., & Shi, W. (2020). Blockchain in global supply chains and cross border trade: A critical synthesis of the state-of-the-art, challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(7), 2082–2099. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1651946>
- Crosby, M. (2016). *BlockChain Technology: Beyond Bitcoin*.
- den Butter, F. A. G., & Mosch, R. H. J. (2003). Trade, Trust and Transaction Costs (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 459501). Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.459501>
- Digital ruble today and tomorrow: Bank of Russia’s report on pilot testing <https://www.cbr.ru/eng/press/event/?id=24743>
- Department of Building Economics, University of Moratuwa, Weerakoon, H. D., Chandanie, H., & Department of Building Economics, University of Moratuwa. (2021). Analysis of Feasibility of Blockchain Technology For International Trade Related To Sri Lankan Construction Industry. *Proceedings of the 9th World Construction Symposium 2021 on Reshaping Construction: Strategic, Structural and Cultural Transformations towards the “Next Normal,”* 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.31705/WCS.2021.7>
- Dyhrberg, A. H. (2016). Bitcoin, gold and the dollar – A GARCH volatility analysis. *Finance Research Letters*, 16, 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2015.10.008>

-
- Galvez, J. F., Mejuto, J. C., & Simal-Gandara, J. (2018). Future challenges on the use of blockchain for food traceability analysis. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 107, 222–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.08.011>
- Ganne, E. (with World Trade Organization). (2018). Can blockchain revolutionize international trade? World Trade Organization. <https://doi.org/10.30875/7c7e7202-en>
- Granger, C. W. J. (1969). Investigating Causal Relations by Econometric Models and Cross-spectral Methods. *Econometrica*, 37(3), 424–438. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1912791>
- Haber, S., & Stornetta, W. S. (1991). How to Time-Stamp a Digital Document. In A. J. Menezes & S. A. Vanstone (Eds.), *Advances in Cryptology-CRYPTO' 90* (pp. 437–455). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-38424-3_32
- Hastig, G. M., & Sodhi, M. S. (2020). Blockchain for Supply Chain Traceability: Business Requirements and Critical Success Factors. *Production and Operations Management*, 29(4), 935–954. <https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.13147>
- Im, K. S., Pesaran, M. H., & Shin, Y. (2003). Testing for unit roots in heterogeneous panels. *Journal of Econometrics*, 115(1), 53–74. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076\(03\)00092-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076(03)00092-7)
- Johansen, S. (1988). Statistical analysis of cointegration vectors. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 12(2–3), 231–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889\(88\)90041-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889(88)90041-3)
- Jouini, J. (2015). Linkage between international trade and economic growth in GCC countries: Empirical evidence from PMG estimation approach. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 24(3), 341–372. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638199.2014.904394>
- Juma, H., Shaalan, K., & Kamel, I. (2019). A Survey on Using Blockchain in Trade Supply Chain Solutions. *IEEE Access*, 7, 184115–184132. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2960542>
- Kandaswamy, R., & Furlonger, D. (n.d.). *Blockchain-Based Transformation: A Gartner Trend Insight Report*.

- Koh, L., Dolgui, A., & Sarkis, J. (2020). Blockchain in transport and logistics – paradigms and transitions. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(7), 2054–2062. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2020.1736428>
- Kshetri, N. (2018). 1 Blockchain's roles in meeting key supply chain management objectives. *International Journal of Information Management*, 39, 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2017.12.005>
- Kumar, S., Shahid, A., & Agarwal, M. (2024). Is BRICS Expansion Significant for Global Trade and GDP? *BRICS Journal of Economics*, 5(4), 5–36. <https://doi.org/10.3897/brics-econ.5.e139877>
- Lian, G. (2022). Research on Credit Algorithm of International Trade Enterprises Based on Blockchain. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022(1), 4768868. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4768868>
- Liu, Z. Z., & Papa, M. (2022). Can BRICS De-dollarize the Global Financial System? Elements in the Economics of Emerging Markets. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009029544>
- Nach, M., & Newadi, R. (2024). BRICS economic integration: Prospects and challenges. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 31(2), 151–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10220461.2024.2380676>
- Nakamoto, S. (2008). Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System.
- Okazaki, Y. (2018). Unveiling the Potential of Blockchain for Customs.
- Öz, S., Gören, HE., (2019). Application of blockchain technology in the supply chain management process: Case studies, *Journal of International Trade, Logistics and Law*, 5(1), pp. 21-27.
- Öz, S., (2020). Genel Teknoloji ve Dijital Dönüşüm Teorisine Giriş, A Chapter in the book, “Teknolojik vee Dijital Dönüşüm”, Ankara, Nobel, pp. 269-292.
- Phillips, P. C. B., & Perron, P. (1988). Testing for a Unit Root in Time Series Regression. *Biometrika*, 75(2), 335–346. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2336182>
- Saberi, S., Kouhizadeh, M., Sarkis, J., & Shen, L. (2019). Blockchain technology and its relationships to sustainable supply chain management. *International Journal of*

- Production Research, 57(7), 2117–2135.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2018.1533261>
- Siddik, Md. N. A., Kabiraj, S., Hosen, Md. E., & Miah, Md. F. (2021). Blockchain Technology and Facilitation of International Trade: An Empirical Analysis. *FIIB Business Review*, 10(3), 232–241. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2319714520968297>
- Siddiqui, K. (2016). Will the Growth of the BRICs Cause a Shift in the Global Balance of Economic Power in the 21st Century? *International Journal of Political Economy*, 45(4), 315–338. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911916.2016.1270084>
- Tapscott, D., & Tapscott, A. (2016). *Blockchain revolution: How the technology behind bitcoin is changing money, business, and the world*. Portfolio / Penguin.
- Tian, X., Zhu, J., Zhao, X., & Wu, J. (2024). Improving operational efficiency through blockchain: Evidence from a field experiment in cross-border trade. *Production Planning & Control*, 35(9), 1009–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2022.2058412>
- Wang, Y., Singgih, M., Wang, J., & Rit, M. (2019). Making sense of blockchain technology: How will it transform supply chains? *International Journal of Production Economics*, 211, 221–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.02.002>
- Ying, W., Jia, S., & Du, W. (2018). Digital enablement of blockchain: Evidence from HNA group. *International Journal of Information Management*, 39, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2017.10.004>
- Yoon, J., Talluri, S., Yildiz, H., & Sheu, C. (2020). The value of Blockchain technology implementation in international trades under demand volatility risk. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(7), 2163–2183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1693651>
- Zheng, Z., Xie, S., Dai, H., Chen, X., & Wang, H. (2017). An Overview of Blockchain Technology: Architecture, Consensus, and Future Trends. 2017 IEEE International Congress on Big Data (BigData Congress), 557–564. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigDataCongress.2017.855G>